

OXIDATION KINETICS OF CARBOXYMETHYLCELLULOSE

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Abstract. Considering the fact that researches on natural polymers are increasing today, this article aims to determine the optimal conditions for obtaining dialdehyde carboxymethylcellulose (DCMC) samples based on sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC) with a high molecular mass and a large amount of aldehyde groups. By carrying out the periodic oxidation reaction in the presence of ultra-high frequency (UHF) rays, the oxidation reaction was carried out for 10 minutes, and DCMC samples containing 82% aldehydes were obtained.

Key words: Dialdehyde carboxymethylcellulose, periodic oxidation, oxidation kinetics, ultra-high frequency rays, aldehyde content, carboxymethylcellulose.

Relevance of the topic. The physic-mechanical and biological properties of the resulting modifications are improved by using natural polymers as crosslinking reagents. In particular, various modifications obtained on the basis of Na-CMC are widely used due to the lack of harmful effects on the body and high biodegradability properties. Nevertheless, in order to increase its reactive activity and expand the possibility of its use in the field of biomedicine, various chemical modifications are considered urgent tasks.

The purpose of the study. Obtaining DCMC samples with a high molecular mass by oxidation with the help UHF and researching the kinetics of the oxidation reaction.

Sodium carboxymethylcellulose (Na-CMC) is a water-soluble form of cellulose, and various oxidants are used to increase its reaction activity. In this case, depending on the type of oxidants, the types of oxidants are different for the products formed [1]. As a result of periodate (NaJO_4) oxidation reactions, covalent bonds of $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_3$ atoms of the pyranose ring are broken and DCMC with an open ring structure is formed [2]. The resulting DCMC is widely used in food, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, biomedicine, as a natural polymer binder [3], and in the synthesis of new types of hydrogels [4].

Research methods. In the newly improved method of synthesizing DCMC, the oxidation reaction of Na-KMS and NaJO_4 is carried out for 10 minutes in the presence of Na-CMC and NaJO_4 in a 1:1 mass ratio, with the $\text{pH}=3.5$ of the solution. The resulting mass is precipitated with organic solvents and filtered. After filtration, DCMC samples are washed 4-7 times with an aqueous solution of alcohol and dried at 37°C until they reach a constant mass.

Results. DCMC samples with the content of aldehydes up to 79%, 10-40%, 30-70%, 85% were synthesized using traditional methods, but the molecular mass of the samples obtained as a result of oxidation in the presence of a strong oxidant had small values. Also, the disadvantage of traditional DCMC synthesis is the long oxidation time and the small molecular mass of the DCMC. Therefore, in order to reduce the oxidation reaction time and maintain the high molecular mass of the obtained DCMC samples, we used UHF to synthesize samples with a large amount of aldehyde groups. The method of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium thiosulfate was used to determine the amount of aldehyde groups in the obtained DCMC samples. The obtained results are presented below (Table 1).

Table-1

Kinetic parameters of the oxidation reaction of Na-CMC samples

Time, min	Aldehyde content, %	N_t	N_0
2	0.34	0.66	1
4	0.58	0.42	
6	0.67	0.33	
8	0.73	0.27	
10	0.82	0.18	
12	0.87	0.13	

Figure 1. Graph of the dependence of the value of aldehydes on time.

The periodic oxidation process was carried out for 2-12 minutes and DCMC samples containing 0.34-0.82 were obtained. The kinetics of the oxidation reaction of Na-CMC samples was studied. It was found that the oxidation reaction is of the first order and the value of the rate constant of the oxidation reaction is equal to 0.1552

The obtained results were studied by infrared spectroscopic method and the intensities typical for aldehyde groups were determined. Generally, the absorbance at about 1740 cm^{-1} is characteristic of aldehydic carbonyl groups, while the band around 880 cm^{-1} is assigned to the formation of hemiacetal bonds between the aldehyde groups and neighbor hydroxyl groups. The band at 1045 cm^{-1} and 1265 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the symmetrical and asymmetrical C-O-C stretching vibration, respectively. The bands at 1324 cm^{-1} , 1418 cm^{-1} and 1597 cm^{-1} are attributed to -CH₂ scissoring, -OH bending vibration and ring stretching of glucose, respectively. The results indicate that the aldehyde group has been introduced into the structure by selective periodate oxidation of CMC.

Conclusion. In this study, a new method of oxidation of Na-CMC samples was presented. In this case, the periodic oxidation process was carried out using UHF rays. As a result of the use of UHF rays, attention was paid to the synthesis of DCMC samples with a high content of aldehyde groups and a high molecular mass. Therefore, in the process of periodic oxidation, the oxidation reaction using UHF rays was selected for 10 minutes, the concentration of the oxidant was 2.5%, the pH of the oxidation reaction was 3.5, and the oxidation temperature of the solution was 30°C . Unlike other homogeneous oxidation reactions, samples containing 82% aldehydes were formed in 10 minutes.

References

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